

STAGES OF THE EMERGENCE AND FORMATION OF UZBEK MYTHS

Akhmedova Madinabonu Makhmudjonovna

Teacher of the Department of the Russian language

At the University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

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Abstract. This article considers the stages of origin and formation of Uzbek myths in the context of oral folk creativity. And also, the author provided examples and analyzing them studied the transformation of the genre myth on the basis of Uzbek folklore.

Key words: folklore, folk art, myth, formation, plot and images

The stages of emergence and formation of Uzbek myths are as follows: 1. Mythological imaginations of the Ural-Altai tribes. It is known that in linguistics there are such concepts as "Altaic language family" and "pro-Altaic language". According to the proponents of the "Altaic theory", the ancient ancestors of the Turkic, Mongolian-Buryat, Tungus-Manchurian (some include Korean and Japanese) peoples actually belonged to a single tribe, which was the "pro-Altaic language" or "who spoke in Proto-Altai dialect. Based on the main conclusions of this theory, we believe that the epic layer, which forms the typological commonality in the folklore of the peoples speaking the Turkic-Mongolian-Buryat-Tungus-Manchurian languages, consists of a series of ancient plots belonging to the Altai period of the history of the oral creativity of these peoples. we count.

The main part of this common epic tradition is the remnants of archaic myths, which historically formed a component of "pro-Altaic folklore" or "pro-Altaic mythology". Uzbek myths (or remnants of myths preserved in the form of a specific plot element, image, motive) whose common variants or similar examples are also found in the oral works of the Mongolian-Buryat and Tungus-Manchurian peoples are included in the "pro-Altaic mythology" belongs to the series of legends. Totemistic myths about the wolf are the most characteristic of the folklore works of this period of the development of Uzbek mythology.

2. Mythology of ancient Turkic peoples. The main part of archaic myths preserved in Uzbek folklore arrived as a result of the epic diffusion of ancient Turkic mythology. Cosmogonic, totemistic, animistic, etiological and ethnogenetic myths, created on the basis of mythological understanding of the world, occupy the main place 3. Mythological ideas related to Zoroastrianism. Many mythical characters such as dragon, giant, fairy, Semurg, Jomard, Aranja

Baba, Ahriman, Aranglar, Zahhok, Siyovush, Hubbi, Ashshadaroz, Sust Xotin, Haidar, which are traditionally used in folklore. its historical foundations go back to Zoroastrian mythology. On the basis of "Avesta" mythology and Zoroastrian rituals, some genres of Uzbek ritual folklore were later formed. The Sust woman ceremony was held in order to call for rain, in order to ensure the abundance of Amudarya water and to prevent the destruction of the flood, the sacrifice of an ox was made in honor of the legendary patron of the Arolcha saint, named after the same name, on Navruz celebrating z holiday, cooking sumak, going to traditional flower parades in the spring season (flower parade, tulip parade, red flower parade, red flower parade, etc.)

Haidar or Ajdar, who is recognized as Baba, calling for the wind, organizing the Ashshadaroz game while cooking sumak, turning the bride and groom around the fire, sprinkling wheat on the graves of the deceased as "birds' rights", crossing the river The historical foundations of traditional ceremonies and customs, such as worshiping Hubbi and throwing salt in water, anointing the horns of oxen before the first goat is sent to the field, are directly connected to the interpretations of Zoroastrianism and "Avesta" mythology in the belief system.

4. Traditions of Arab-Islamic mythology. It is known that Movarounnahr was conquered by the Arabs at the end of the 7th century, and this process ended in the middle of the 8th century. As a result, the religion of Islam, which spread to this country, brought to Central Asia plots, motifs and images belonging to the epic traditions of the mythology and folklore of the peoples of the East. Although the composition of Islamic mythology is multi-layered, it includes core myths (Arabic myths) and assimilated myths (i.e. folklore of later conquered peoples and myths related to other religious views). in, its foundation was formed by examples of oral creativity of ancient Arab peoples. As a result of the epic influence of the plot of Arab folk books, narratives and legends, many new works were created in the folklore of the peoples of Central Asia. The mythological imagination of our ancestors was enriched by the system of characters related to Arab-Islamic myths. In particular, the first source of mythologies such as anqo, jinn, ghul, Odami Od, Morut, Lot, Manot, Kohi Qaf, Eram is actually in Arab folklore.

So, the historical foundations of Uzbek mythology go back to the religious views belonging to the lowest stages of the past of our ancestors. The first layer of mythological beliefs was directly related to the totemistic, animistic and dualistic imaginations of our ancestors who lived in ancient times, beliefs based

on magical beliefs, as well as ancient cults embodying the mystical understanding of nature and the idea of fertility. As a result of the gradual development of ancient myths over the centuries, dualistic myths depicting the struggle between good and evil, cosmogonic myths expressing folk views about the creation and end of the universe, astral myths about sky lights, and the debate about the emergence of time accounting practices a system of leading calendar myths, ethnogenetic myths explaining the origin of clans and tribes, and anthropogenic myths describing the adventures of extraordinary heroes was formed.

The achievement of independence of Uzbekistan created great opportunities to study folklore works related to ancient imaginations, including mythological plots and motifs on a large scale. In particular, the role of mythology and mythological images in the genesis of ritual folklore in Uzbek folklore, the role of mythology in the Uzbek folk epic and the diffusion of myths, the system of mythological images in Uzbek folklore have been widely studied. The concept of "Uzbek mythology" was introduced into folklore, and it was scientifically substantiated that it is a component of Turkic mythology and embodies the beliefs, imagination and beliefs of the ancient inhabitants of Central Asia.

3. Genres of legend, narration, narrative. There are important theoretical issues in each discipline and field. The science that studies fiction is called literary studies. We call the field of studying folk oral poetic creation folklore. Although folklore studies is considered an independent discipline within literary studies, there are a number of general and common aspects due to the fact that the object of study is fiction. In particular, the issue of genres is important for both literary studies and folklore studies. Only in literary studies, such as ghazal, rubai, dostan, noma belonging to representatives of written literature (classical literature); Genre features of poems, stories, novels, dramas (modern literature) are studied. In folklore studies, the peculiarities of such genres as proverbs, songs, tales, and epics in folk literature are studied. However, regardless of the form of literature, achievements and discoveries in each direction are evaluated as a contribution to the development of the science of literature.

The legend is taken from the Persian language in the essence of meaning, two concepts lead: 1 - to tell an event, scene; 2 - this story is fictional, consists of textures. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language at the beginning, several meanings of the word are indicated: "to be a legend", "to weave a legend", "legendary", etc. But the main meaning is related to the fantasy of

thought, the mind the concept of telling incredible fictitious events and thereby gaining fame is leading. In the content of legends, the oldest fictitious events, toponymic information explaining the name of a specific area are given", "Oshoba", "Qanqus" and other examples reflect such topics.

During the folklore expedition, we had the opportunity to record amazing legends about almost every village, spring, hill, water source. Unlike fairy tales 36 they do not observe the stability of the plot system. Their subject line can be analyzed into three: 1. Pure mythological legends.

2. Legends explaining historical events.

3. Myths related to geographical names in local areas.

Legends, as the first example of artistic creation, served to create a sense of confidence in the human heart, hope that every person can find happiness as a result of his own abilities and actions. For example, the concept of fate has existed in people's minds since ancient times. A person accepted every unpleasant problem as fate. However, there are legends in which it is said that a person's behavior, intention, especially a sharp decision, can change his fate with a prayer. So, in terms of content, legends consist mainly of fictions with a very simple plot that conveys information. In them, the creation of the nation, the appearance of the sun, moon, stars, and planets in the universe, the explanation of geographical names, the review of various historical events, paintings and drawings find their expression. From ancient times, our ancestors had a conscious attitude to every question, every problem, traditions and customs of their lives, and even to the homeland where they live, and expressed their final conclusions and experiences through legends, among other genres of folklore.

The study of legends in folklore allows to determine the theoretical and practical aspects of the history of oral creation. Stories. This word is taken from the Arabic language and means a story. Narratives differ from legends in their closeness to life. If the events that cannot happen in the legends are told, then the events in the stories often tell about specific episodes in the lives of historical figures, famous scholars, and statesmen. Sometimes when we hear a story, we fully believe that it will happen, sometimes we may not believe the story, even if it is free of a special fantastic image.

Therefore, it is difficult to define a sharp difference between legend and narrative. In any case, based on many years of experience, it can be said that it is appropriate to accept a story that is believed as a legend, and one that cannot be believed as a myth. Because there is no difference between legends and

narratives in terms of content and plot system. Only narrations are considered to be historical evidence, evidence. Narratives belong to the epic genus, like legends, according to the story they reflect. They are short in size. The length of the text is short, and the number of scenes presented is limited. The artistic image is not overemphasized, because the narrative is the priority in them. According to the direction of the content, historical events are divided into narratives created on the basis of the courage or betrayal of the people who participated in them, or to explain the naming of places in the regions of our country. In historical narratives, the bravery of the people who sacrificed their lives for the freedom and independence of their country, such as Tomaris, Shiroq, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, and Amir Temur, and at the same time, Dalvarzin, Guldursun, who betrayed their country for the sake of their fleeting lust, The stories of treacherous persons are told..

Neither the deeds of the brave nor the treachery of traitors will be forgotten. Another type of narratives is distinguished by the names of places in local areas. The important thing is that in such narratives, the focus is not on the fantastic aspects of the described story, but on the qualities of observing life, coming to the right conclusions, and using the mind. The following conclusions can be drawn from the opinions expressed about the narratives:

1. Narratives, unlike legends, are based on real-life events.
2. They are thematically divided into types and either describe an important event in the life of a historical person or explain the name of a geographical place.
3. In narratives, more attention is paid to the description of the event in a short and concise, simple and fluent manner than in the artistic image. In fact, it is precisely these qualities that determine the artistic nature of narratives. You can see beautiful examples of narratives in classical literature and modern Uzbek literature.

The term naql has existed among the peoples of Central Asia since ancient times and has different meanings. At first, some genres of folklore were called by this name. It happened in the literary process and appeared at the core of the culture, moral philosophy, and thinking of the Turkic peoples. Zarbulmasal is an Arabic word that means to hit (criticize) the guilty with a parable. Muhammad Jobalrudi (XVII century) used this word as synonyms of parable and parable, and in another place, he gave it in the sense of a symbolic story. In "Ghiyas ul-lugat" it is defined as the carrier of one or another figurative meaning in speech. In Uzbek folk prose, a parable is called a parable. Zarbulmasal was originally a

separate genre of written literature. It was later referred to as a parable. Narrative is a proverb in Russian folklore. In Persian, naql means parable, aqol (allegory), in Tajik it means fairy tale, matal, proverb, in Turkmen it is called naql-topishmaq, in Kazakh and Kyrgyz it is called metel.

In the folklore of the Turkic peoples, works belonging to different genres are narrated. In particular, there are cases of quoting fairy tales, legends, narratives, epics, proverbs, proverbs, and even riddles written in old records, folk books, and manuscripts. That is probably why a fairy tale is called a fairy tale in Azerbaijan. Narrative means an oral story. Basically, it is an Arabic word that has three different meanings: the first is movement, movement, that is, events and events with a movable meaning are called by this name. The second is to tell a story, to tell a story; thirdly, separate genres of oral prose, short story, fairy tale, and matal are treated as narratives as a whole. These genres are close to each other, they are equaled by figurative meaning, allegory.

So, the metaphorical meaning is a general, at the same time, the main and decisive sign for proverbs, sayings, parables, proverbs, and riddles. A proverb is basically a set of wise thoughts and teachings. Therefore, it is a story that creates philosophical generalizations from life events and events, and describes exemplary behavior and behavior in a metaphorical way. So, narration glorifies intelligence, manners, and wisdom, and allows understanding and evaluation. One is a teller, narrator, and the other means a story. Initially, stories, proverbs, fairy tales, proverbs, riddles, epics were also referred to as narratives. Naqil means the one who tells about morals and etiquette norms that are worthy of example. Narrative works mainly fulfill an educational and aesthetic function. That is why it is called "Naql - the mine of intelligence". Tales, epics, proverbs, and riddles have been referred to in one word in ancient times.

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